

Campylobacteriosis: an immunity-focused view

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Abstract

Campylobacteriosis is a debilitating and widespread gastrointestinal disease in both developed and developing countries. In spite of very significant attention to control contamination of food products, relatively little progress has been made in curbing human illness. We propose that differences in human susceptibility, especially via an adaptive immunity response, is a key factor to unravel the continuing, widespread and baffling trends in incidence of campylobacteriosis. This recognizes that Campylobacter species are widespread in the environment (a so-called miasma view) and that although the focus on select contaminated foods has not been definitive, it may provide a means to develop a specific/defined geographic region community-wide immunity approach.

Introduction

Campylobacteriosis is the most common bacterial cause of gastrointestinal disease in humans, with chicken meat regarded as the most common source for human infection (Altekruse et al., 1999; Butzler, 2004; Kotula & Stern, 1984; Nauta et al., 2009; Skirrow, 1991). The disease frequently results in severe diarrhoea, while sequelae may include various forms of paralysis and potentially death e.g. reactive arthritis and Guillain-Barré syndrome (Nichols et al., 2012; Skirrow, 1977). Notably, incidence is primarily sporadic, with relatively few cases associated with outbreaks.

There is a common acceptance that poultry meat products are the most common source of *Campylobacter* infection in humans with one species, *C. jejuni*, typically reported in 80-90% of cases, the balance being primarily *C. coli* with a range of other species being far less common (Altekruse et al., 1999). The current consensus and public health focus is predominantly towards reduction of *Campylobacter*-contamination in chicken products (Umaraw et al., 2017).

This consensus view is supported by some very strong observational and experimental data. However, there remains a plethora of other sources and explanations for campylobacteriosis that make this consensus view problematic (Nelson & Harris, 2017). Faecal contamination by animals and birds is widespread in soil, waterways, irrigated crops, etc as best evidenced by ubiquitous *Escherichia coli* isolation (Edberg et al., 2000). At present, advances in biotyping, especially molecular identification, are providing critical source/patient linkage information. However, this is simply one aspect of the historical competition between germ and miasma theories of disease (Loomis & Wing, 1990). Epidemiological studies need to embrace a wider, broader range of disciplines and views than just risk analysis (Susser, 1998).

The concept of a 'miasma' viewpoint has been suggested to be unhelpful towards reducing the disease burden of campylobacteriosis (Wilson et al., 2006). However, if the single source concept is not producing

sufficient results (Nelson & Harris, 2017), perhaps we should consider a broader scope of investigation.

We reconsider campylobacteriosis epidemiology and attempt a rational alternative view to the current risk analysis focus. Specifically that campylobacteriosis sporadic incidence patterns arise primarily as a result of differences in individual immune susceptibility plus microbe exposure.

Immune Susceptibility

Relatively large proportions of any population exhibit or develop comparative immunodeficiencies and are therefore more vulnerable to diseases (Lund & O'Brien, 2011). These are commonly the very young, elderly or otherwise immune-compromised individuals. Use of antibiotics appears also to increase susceptibility to infection, especially when used in the period 1 month to 2 years prior to infection (Koningstein et al., 2011; Neal et al., 1996).

Proton pump inhibitors have long been recognised to increase risk for campylobacteriosis (Bouwknegt et al., 2014; Neal et al., 1996; Tam et al., 2009; Wei et al., 2017). The slight increase in campylobacteriosis rates in the elderly is commonly thought to be associated with a natural age associated reduced stomach acidity, but evidence indicates this seldom occurs (Hurwitz et al., 1997). Therefore other risk factors in this age group also need to be investigated. Differences in dietary fibre intake appears to affect the ability of *Campylobacter* to invade gut epithelium cells (Masanta et al., 2013), possibly through changing the concentration of short chain fatty acids (SCFA) derived from the gut microbiota.

Campylobacter outbreak cases are much less common and typically involve a larger group of cases clustered via a common point source. This may be from specific food stuffs, such as liver (Edwards et al., 2014), commercial catering (Mazick et al., 2006; Osimani & Clementi, 2016), dairy products (Taylor et al., 2013) and contaminated water sources (Gallay et al., 2006; Kuusi et al., 2004). Therefore outbreaks probably represent increased opportunity for infection by providing an infectious dose

sufficiently large to overwhelm innate and/or adaptive protective mechanisms of most people.

Susceptibility to infection in a campylobacteriosis context can therefore relate to one or more specific changes. These include:

- reduced immune response to infection induced by disease, pathogen or medication associated immunodeficiencies
- prior use of antibiotics
- changes in natural barriers to infection such as proton pump inhibitor medication
- opportunity for infection as clearly evidenced in outbreak case clusters, i.e. overwhelming infectious dose or novel strains.

Immunity

An innate immune reaction to *Campylobacter* infections has been suggested previously. For example “individual susceptibility” (Rodrigues et al., 2000), “previous exposure may confer protection against subsequent infection” (Forbes et al., 2009), and “population immunity” (Nichols et al., 2012). Development of such immune reactions is already exploited in animal health (Sahin et al., 2017) against *Campylobacter* in ovine (Fenwick et al., 2000) and bovine (Hoffer, 1981) farming using commercially available vaccines, suggesting an opportunity for human protection too (Scott, 1997; Tribble et al., 2010). An equivalent vaccination for chickens, while receiving considerable investment, has failed to prove as effective (De Zoete et al., 2007; Meunier et al., 2016).

Specific immune responses in humans to *Campylobacter* infection have been reported (Baqar et al., 2001; Cawthraw et al., 2002). Surveys indicate an apparent immunity associated with prior and continued exposure, for example through occupational exposure (Cawthraw et al., 2000; De Perio et al., 2013; Ellström et al., 2014; Vegosen et al., 2015; Wilson, 2004), including dose-response development of immunity markers. Sero-epidemiological surveys indicate very high exposure to *Campylobacter* infection by early adulthood within European populations (Ang et al., 2007; Ang et al., 2011; Teunis et al., 2013). However, any immunity from prior exposure appears to be strain specific (Kirkpatrick et al., 2013), is dose related and degrades fairly rapidly (Tribble et al., 2010).

Within developing countries, immunity markers are prevalent in older populations without associated diarrhoea symptoms (Coker et al., 2002; Havelaar et al., 2009). This effect is presumably associated with continued exposure and maintenance boosting of immunity, similar to that reported through occupational exposure in developed countries.

Discussion

Humans are exposed to a very wide range of species and biotypes of *Campylobacter*, from very broadly defined sources and via mechanisms clearly far wider than food contamination (Nelson & Harris, 2017). Within this exposure pattern, individuals also vary in susceptibility. A broader discussion beyond simply controlling

Campylobacter contamination in specific food sources is required in order to tackle combating campylobacteriosis.

Recognition of the presence of an immune response reaction in humans indicates the potential for some sort of prophylactic immune-system priming. Development of killed whole-cell vaccine for oral treatment has shown promise in animal models (Baqar et al., 1995), but vaccines for human use remain problematic (Jagusztyn-Krynicka et al., 2009). Whole-cell killed vaccines have shown particular promise against other diseases, especially where there is endemicity and an environmental exposure, such as those against *Cholera* (Kirpich et al., 2017) or *Helicobacter pylori* (both vibrios and so close relatives of *Campylobacter*) (Summerton et al., 2010).

In some respects, properly cooked (*Campylobacter*) contaminated foodstuffs could in fact prove to have the same whole-cell killed vaccine effect (Tam et al., 2009), thus explaining the source of frequent exposure without illness as evidenced by sero-epidemiology studies (Teunis et al., 2013). Thus, in a counter intuitive manner, the current efforts to eradicate *Campylobacter* from chicken products may in fact prove counterproductive in some respects by reducing the frequency of our ongoing exposure and immune priming to the bacteria. This prior immune priming may provide some protection against larger infectious dose cases, including outbreaks, but still largely does not explain the much larger proportion of sporadic cases.

The benefit of killed whole-cell vaccines is that a broad range of biotypes, typical of the specific region targeted for protection, can probably be developed relatively quickly and cheaply. Medication via a common food, such as a milk drink or freeze-dried formulation for oral dosage, might prove one means of establishing population-level immunity. In particular, increased risk immuno-compromised groups might obtain particular benefit from such protective treatment. The relatively high incidence of campylobacteriosis in travellers could similarly be addressed by oral dosage of locally prepared ‘medicated’ food or drink when travelling. Eating properly cooked local produce could also be expected to provide more immunity to more commonly encountered local environmental strains. Interestingly, this approach would support the ‘Slow Food’ movement which encourages farming of plants, seeds, and livestock characteristic of the local ecosystem.

The two most common environmental species of *Campylobacter*, *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* (Jones et al., 2017) are the most likely to infect local chicken production facilities. This presumably then means regular consumption of properly cooked chicken foods derived from infected chickens has quite possibly been acting as a natural killed whole-cell vaccine for the human population also exposed to the same environmental *Campylobacter* strains. Broad strain variation load and early colonisation is common in free-range flocks, unlike common single strain colonisation in high density flocks (Cawthraw & Newell, 2010).

However, modern increased biosecurity practices in mass poultry meat production is both removing this vaccine option through aiming for *Campylobacter*-free

meat production, and severely curtailing the range of local environmental strains encountered. This raises interesting ethical dilemmas, if this common food product has such a community-wide immune stimulating protective potential, then deliberately introducing practices, such as free-range farming, in order that a wide range of local environmental strains of *Campylobacter* are present at slaughter makes sense. However, this could also increase the risks of point source outbreak and other cross-contamination events occurring.

Conclusion

While it is sometimes difficult to establish a specific source, outbreaks of campylobacteriosis are generally clear cut and essentially resolve to specific point sources. The far higher incidence of sporadic cases is more problematic to explain, especially considering the difficulties with security of source attribution via poultry meat contamination, although there is little doubt this is very likely to be a contributing source. However, the emphasis on attempting to control poultry as the primary source has so far contributed relatively little to reducing the incidence of campylobacteriosis in the long term.

Advances in understanding of immune responses, not only for the development of vaccines in animals, but also understanding the otherwise baffling sporadic incidence pattern in humans, may contribute far more. In this regard, recognising the broad environmental prevalence of *Campylobacter* species via a 'miasma' view, and applying an immunological lens, may move the debate forward. It could return the focus to reducing the incidence of campylobacteriosis, by understanding the environmental ubiquity of the bacteria and associated ongoing priming of our immune system rather than attempting to eliminate this organism from food sources that has so far been only modestly effective.

Failure to embrace this concept is more likely to entrench the current chicken source only belief concept approach which 'is a riddle, wrapped in a mystery, inside an enigma' (Churchill, 1939); but perhaps there is a key, in this framework of a 'miasma'-induced immunity.

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References

- Altekruse SF, Stern NJ, Fields PI, Swerdlow DL (1999) *Campylobacter jejuni*—an emerging foodborne pathogen. *Emerg Infect Dis* 5: 28-35.
- Ang C, van Pelt W, Teunis P, Herbrink P, Keijser J et al. (2007) Sero-epidemiology indicates frequent and repeated exposure to *Campylobacter* during childhood. *Zoonoses Public Health* 54S: 50.
- Ang CW, Teunis PFM, Herbrink P, Keijser J, Van Duynhoven YHTP et al. (2011) Sero-epidemiological studies indicate frequent and repeated exposure to *Campylobacter* spp. during childhood. *Epidemiol Infect* 139: 1361-1368.
- Baqar S, Rice B, Lee L, Bourgeois AL, Amina NED et al. (2001) *Campylobacter jejuni* enteritis. *Clinical Infectious Diseases* 33: 901.
- Bouwknegt M, van Pelt W, Kubbinga ME, Weda M, Havelaar AH (2014) Potential association between the recent increase in campylobacteriosis incidence in the Netherlands and proton-pump inhibitor use - an ecological study. *Euro Surveill* 19: 21-26.
- Butzler J (2004) *Campylobacter*, from obscurity to celebrity. *Clin Microbiol Infect* 10: 868-876.
- Cawthraw S, Lind L, Kaijser B, Newell D (2000) Antibodies, directed towards *Campylobacter jejuni* antigens, in sera from poultry abattoir workers. *Clinical & Experimental Immunology* 122: 55-60.
- Cawthraw SA, Feldman RA, Sayers AR, Newell DG (2002) Long-term antibody responses following human infection with *Campylobacter jejuni*. *Clin Exp Immunol* 130: 101-106.
- Coker AO, Isokpehi RD, Thomas BN, Amisu KO, Obi CL (2002) Human campylobacteriosis in developing countries. *Emerg Infect Dis* 8: 237-244.
- De Perio M, Niemeier R, Levine S, Gruszynski K, Gibbins J (2013) *Campylobacter* infection in poultry-processing workers, Virginia, USA, 2008–2011. *Emerging infectious diseases* 19: 286-288.
- De Zoete MR, Van Putten JPM, Wagenaar JA (2007) Vaccination of chickens against *Campylobacter*. *Vaccine* 25: 5548-5557.
- Edberg SC, Rice EW, Karlin RJ, Allen MJ (2000) *Escherichia coli*: the best biological drinking water indicator for public health protection. *Journal of Applied Microbiology* 88: 106S-116S.
- Edwards DS, Milne LM, Morrow K, Sheridan P, Verlander NQ et al. (2014) Campylobacteriosis outbreak associated with consumption of undercooked chicken liver pâté in the East of England, September 2011: identification of a dose-response risk. *Epidemiol Infect* 142: 352-357.
- Ellström P, Hansson I, Söderström C, Olsson Engvall E, Rautelin H (2014) A prospective follow-up study on transmission of *Campylobacter* from poultry to abattoir workers. *Foodborne Pathog Dis* 11: 684-688.
- Fenwick S, West D, Hunter J, Sargison N, Ahmed F et al. (2000) *Campylobacter fetus fetus* abortions in vaccinated ewes. *New Zealand Veterinary Journal* 48: 155-157.
- Forbes KJ, Gormley FJ, Dallas JF, Labovitiadi O, MacRae M et al. (2009) *Campylobacter* immunity and co-infection following a large outbreak in a farming community. *J Clin Microbiol* 47: 111-116.
- Gallay A, De Valk H, Cournot M, Ladeuil B, Hemery C et al. (2006) A large multi-pathogen waterborne community outbreak linked to faecal contamination of a groundwater system, France, 2000. *Clin Microbiol Infect* 12: 561-570.

- Havelaar AH, van Pelt W, Ang CW, Wagenaar JA, van Putten JPM et al. (2009) Immunity to *Campylobacter*: its role in risk assessment and epidemiology. *Crit Rev Microbiol* 35: 1-22.
- Hoffer MA (1981) Bovine campylobacteriosis: a review. *Canadian Veterinary Journal* 22: 327-330.
- Hurwitz A, Brady DA, Schaal S, Samloff I, Dedon J et al. (1997) Gastric acidity in older adults. *JAMA* 278: 659-662.
- Kirkpatrick BD, Lyon CE, Porter CK, Maue AC, Guerry P et al. (2013) Lack of homologous protection against *Campylobacter jejuni* CG8421 in a human challenge model. *Clinical Infectious Diseases* 57: 1106-1113.
- Koningstein M, Simonsen J, Helms M, Hald T, Mølbak K (2011) Antimicrobial use: A risk factor or a protective factor for acquiring campylobacteriosis? *Clinical Infectious Diseases* 53: 644-650.
- Kotula AW, Stern NJ (1984) The importance of *Campylobacter jejuni* to the meat industry: a review. *J Anim Sci* 58: 1561-1566.
- Kuusi M, Klemets P, Miettinen I, Laaksonen I, Sarkkinen H et al. (2004) An outbreak of gastroenteritis from a non-chlorinated community water supply. *J Epidemiol Community Health* 58: 273-277.
- Loomis D, Wing S (1990) Is molecular epidemiology a germ theory for the end of the twentieth century? *International Journal of Epidemiology* 19: 1-3.
- Lund BM, O'Brien SJ (2011) The occurrence and prevention of foodborne disease in vulnerable people. *Foodborne Pathogens and Disease* 8: 961-973.
- Masanta WO, Heimesaat MM, Bereswill S, Tareen AM, Lugert R et al. (2013) Modification of intestinal microbiota and its consequences for innate immune response in the pathogenesis of campylobacteriosis. *Clin Dev Immunol* 2013: 526860.
- Mazick A, Ethelberg S, Nielsen EM, Mølbak K, Lisby M (2006) An outbreak of *Campylobacter jejuni* associated with consumption of chicken, Copenhagen, 2005.. *Euro Surveill* 11: 137-139.
- Meunier M, Guyard-Nicodème M, Hirchaud E, Parra A, Chemaly M et al. (2016) Identification of novel vaccine candidates against *Campylobacter* through reverse vaccinology. *Journal of Immunology Research* 2016: 9.
- Nauta M, Hill A, Rosenquist H, Brynstad S, Fetsch A et al. (2009) A comparison of risk assessments on *Campylobacter* in broiler meat. *Int J Food Microbiol* 129: 107-123.
- Neal KR, Scott HM, Slack RCB, Logan RFA (1996) Omeprazole as a risk factor for *Campylobacter* gastroenteritis: case-control study. *BMJ* 312: 414-415.
- Nelson WR, Harris B (2017) Campylobacteriosis – the problem with chicken-as-source. Zenodo: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.853494>.
- Nichols GL, Richardson JF, Sheppard SK, Lane C, Sarran C (2012) *Campylobacter* epidemiology: a descriptive study reviewing 1 million cases in England and Wales between 1989 and 2011. *BMJ Open* 2: e001179.
- Osimani A, Clementi F (2016) The catering industry as a source of campylobacteriosis in Europe—A review. *International Journal of Hospitality Management* 54: 68 - 74.
- Rodrigues LC, Cowden JM, Wheeler JG, Sethi D, Wall PG et al. (2000) The study of infectious intestinal disease in England: risk factors for cases of infectious intestinal disease with *Campylobacter jejuni* infection.. *Epidemiol Infect* 127: 185-193.
- Sahin O, Yaeger M, Wu Z, Zhang Q (2017) *Campylobacter*-associated diseases in animals. *Annual Review of Animal Biosciences* 5: 21-42.
- Scott DA (1997) Vaccines against *Campylobacter jejuni*. *The Journal of Infectious Diseases* 176: S183.
- Skirrow MB (1977) *Campylobacter* enteritis: a new disease. *BMJ* 2: 9-11.
- Skirrow MB (1991) Epidemiology of *Campylobacter* enteritis. *Int J Food Microbiol* 12: 9-16.
- Susser M (1998) Does risk factor epidemiology put epidemiology at risk? Peering into the future. *Journal of Epidemiology & Community Health* 52: 608-611.
- Tam CC, Higgins CD, Neal KR, Rodrigues LC, Millership SE et al. (2009) Chicken consumption and use of acid-suppressing medications as risk factors for *Campylobacter* enteritis, England. *Emerging Infectious Diseases* 15: 1402-1408.
- Taylor EV, Herman KM, Ailes EC, Fitzgerald C, Yoder JS et al. (2013) Common source outbreaks of *Campylobacter* infection in the USA, 1997-2008. *Epidemiol Infect* 141: 987-996.
- Teunis PFM, Falkenhorst G, Ang CW, Strid MA, DE Valk H et al. (2013) *Campylobacter* seroconversion rates in selected countries in the European Union. *Epidemiol Infect* 141: 2051-2057.
- Tribble DR, Baqar S, Scott DA, Oplinger ML, Trespalacios F et al. (2010) Assessment of the duration of protection in *Campylobacter jejuni* experimental infection in humans. *Infection and Immunity* 78: 1750-1759.
- Umaraw P, Prajapati A, Verma AK, Pathak V, Singh VP (2017) Control of *Campylobacter* in poultry industry from farm to poultry processing unit: A review. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition* 57: 659-665.
- Vegosen L, Breyse PN, Agnew J, Gray GC, Nachamkin I et al. (2015) Occupational exposure to swine, poultry, and cattle and antibody biomarkers of *Campylobacter jejuni* exposure and autoimmune peripheral neuropathy. *PLoS One* 10: e0143587.
- Wei L, Ratnayake L, Phillips G, McGuigan CC, Morant SV et al. (2017) Acid-suppression medications and bacterial gastroenteritis: a population-based cohort study. *Br J Clin Pharmacol* 83: 1298-1308.
- Wilson IG (2004) Airborne *Campylobacter* infection in a poultry worker: case report and review of the literature. *Communicable Disease and Public Health* 7: 349-353.
- Wilson N, Baker M, Simmons G, Shoemack P (2006) New Zealand should control *Campylobacter* in fresh poultry before worrying about flies. *N Z Med J* 119: U2242.